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THE USE OF AUTHENTIC AUDIO AND VIDEO MATERIALS IN TEACHING STUDENTS OF A NON-LINGUIETIC UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: The article is devoted to teaching a foreign language to students of non-linguistic universities, in particular, the use of authentic material in the learning process as a part of the curriculum. The relevance of the study lies in the fact that one of the main difficulties for many students of non-linguistic universities in the process of learning a foreign language is the language barrier, and the use of modern technologies and authentic audio and video materials in foreign language classes allows the teacher to make classes rich, interesting, informative and contribute to the removal of the psychological barrier. The effectiveness of using this material consists in individualization and motivation to learn. Authentic audio and video materials are a sample of speech and language, special and general cultural vocabulary, which contribute to a more accelerated and effective assimilation of the material by students in foreign language classes. Possession of professional authentic terminology, maintenance of the communication process on professional topics, the ability to understand texts on the chosen specialty, knowledge of the values and qualities of representatives of a foreign-speaking society is part of the professional competence of the future specialist. Therefore, this article is aimed at using authentic audio and video materials in the study of authentic terminology of students of non-linguistic universities.

Keywords: teaching a foreign language, authentic audio and video material, language barrier.

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АУТЕНТИЧНОГО АУДИО- И ВИДЕОМАТЕРИАЛА В ОБУЧЕНИИ СТУДЕНТОВ НЕЯЗЫКОВОГО ВУЗА

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Аннотация: Статья посвящена преподаванию иностранного языка студентам неязыковых ВУЗов, в частности, использованию аутентичного материала в процессе обучения в рамках учебной программы. Актуальность исследования заключается в том, что одной из главных трудностей у многих студентов неязыковых ВУЗов в процессе обучения иностранному языку является языковой барьер, а использование современных технологий и аутентичного аудио- и видеоматериала на занятиях иностранных языков позволяет преподавателю сделать занятия насыщенными, интересными, информативными и способствуют снятию психологического барьера. Эффективность использования данного материала состоит в индивидуализации и мотивации к обучению. Аутентичные аудио- и видеоматериалы представляют собой образец речи и языка, специальную и общекультурную лексику, которые способствуют более ускоренному и эффективному усвоению материала студентами на занятиях иностранного языка. Владение профессиональной аутентичной терминологией, поддержание коммуникативного процесса на профессиональные темы, умение понимать тексты по выбранной специальности, знание ценностей и качеств представителей иноязычного общества входит в профессиональную компетенцию будущего специалиста. Следовательно, данная статья направлена на использование аутентичного аудио- и видеоматериала в изучении аутентичной терминологии студентов неязыковых ВУЗов.

Ключевые слова: преподавание иностранного языка, аутентичный аудио-и видеоматериал, языковой барьер.

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Through language, you can express any thought using different linguistic means. The most important component of teaching a foreign language is the educational program at universities. When teaching a foreign language, different methods and means are used, where one of the most common means can be called the use of video materials.

The concept of "authenticity" has entered the methodology of teaching a foreign language with the spread of a communicative approach in order to bring the learning process as close as possible to natural communication. Exploring the ways and methods of effective teaching of foreign languages, pedagogy has gone a long and winding way, based on the achievements of technological progress, logic, semiotics and psychology.

The video allows you to teach foreign language communication taking into account various sociolinguistic factors presented with the help of visual information and largely determining the nature of speech utterances of communicants, namely: their social status, the nature of relationships, spatial and temporal conditions of communication, etc.

Based on this fact, a new stage in the history of teaching has become the use of authentic audiovisual forms of learning that combine visual and auditory perceptual components.

Communicative training plays an important role in teaching a foreign language. Students need to get an idea of the life and traditions of the studied language. To solve this problem, the Internet is involved. It should be noted that one of the main difficulties for many students is the language barrier, in particular, the psychological characteristics are affected, but modern technologies allow the teacher to make classes richer, more interesting and informative.

At the present stage of education, the requirements for the level of training of specialists are increasing, because the possession of professional authentic terminology is gaining more and more relevance in the modern world compared to specialists who simply speak a foreign language. Graduates of non-linguistic universities need not only to know their subject well, but also to know the stylistic and theoretical aspects of the language of their orientation in order to carry out their professional activities qualitatively.

Possession of professional authentic terminology, maintenance of the communicative process on

professional topics, the ability to understand texts on the chosen specialty, knowledge of the values and qualities of representatives of a foreign-speaking society is part of the professional competence of a future specialist. Therefore, this article is devoted not only to the study of the use of authentic audio and video materials in teaching students of a non-linguistic university, but also aims to introduce additional material in the study of authentic terminology of students of non-linguistic universities.

The above aspects determine the relevance of the chosen topic. The purpose of this article is to study and effectively assimilate professional vocabulary within the framework of the curriculum using authentic audio and video materials in training.

So, for example, Galskova N.D., Gez N.I. write about the psychological characteristic of listening, which lies in the fact that it is a complex, receptive mental-mnemonic activity associated with the perception and active performance of processing information of oral speech communication. This form of oral communication is not yet sufficiently developed, which can be explained by the following factors.

Firstly, listening is considered to be a secondary product of oral speech, because it is used sporadically in the classroom and in situations that are far from authentic. The authentic situation is a "real context of a foreign culture", respectively, with materials that are compiled by native speakers for native speakers. [3, p. 161]. Secondly, sometimes not all teachers are aware of the psychological and linguistic difficulties of listening.

It should be noted that there is contact and remote listening. Contact listening is the main part of oral interactive communication, and remote listening is an independent form of communication (for example: radio, television, etc.).

Studies by Russian and foreign psychologists show that the listener (a student) relies on his/her own experience and developed psychological mechanisms when listening. "Taking information of the phonological (lower) level, he must recode it into units of the conceptual (high) level, using various supports of perception, including the prompting function of situations ..." [14, p. 191].

The audiovisual method is also one of the valuable teaching tools, because when watching a film, a student understands how a foreign language is used in real life. The visual series shows the linguistic

and paralinguistic aspects of the behavior of native speakers in a real life. This method performs a cognitive function, helping students to get acquainted with the history of the country and culture. Thus, this process is personal and complex, because it depends on such factors as: the development of speech hearing and memory, the ability to predict, the presence of attention and interest. [6, p. 38].

Kraevsky V.V., Khutorskoy A.V. stated that a phrase, when perceived by ear, is understood as a result of recognition of informative signs, and intonation is considered to be the most informative sign. Intonation includes "perceived qualities" that can be divided into speech, syntactic blocks, so the student will be able to understand the connection of parts of the phrase and the content. In the communicative aspect of the utterance, intonation is the main structural feature that distinguishes the communicative types of sentences, namely: narration, question, exclamation, prompting. Logical stress and division of the phrase into syntagmas are included in the logical and syntactic plan of the sentence. The understanding of the subtext is facilitated by an emotional assessment, which is also expressed by intonation. Thus, intonation hearing produces indicator signs that are necessary for a short-term memory. [9, p. 191].

Listening is a complex process of searching and selecting informative features, which depends on the presence of associative connections in the listener. It is clear that the perception of speech in the native language is easy, but foreign speech forces the listener to work, not only with a productive vocabulary, but also to use the receptive skills that we acquire when reading. Because the visual image of the word does not always coincide with the auditory image.

Authentic video materials, according to Fedorova M.A., solve important tasks of training, education and upbringing in the classroom. Students have the opportunity to hear authentic speech of native speakers, which creates the effect of live communication. This is an important fact for our country, because some of the students do not have the opportunity to travel abroad to practice. [15].

An important fact of using video materials in the classroom is the individualization of learning and motivation to learn. Video recordings include special vocabulary (in our case, professional terminology), which contributes to the study of pronunciation, memorization of lexical units in certain communication situations. Thus, video materials create favorable

conditions for the formation of both communicative and socio-cultural competence.

Learning a foreign language in a high school is aimed at developing both communicative skills and lexical, grammatical, phonetic and graphic skills. These aspects of speech activity will not be formed without full mastery of vocabulary in the classroom. Thus, the selection of lexical units and the systematization of the selected material during listening is one of the main components.

According to research, out of thousands of word-formation and syntactic models, only about 200-300 are used in real life. [11]. Sets of certain grammatical models used by native speakers make up the lexical minimum which is necessary for learning. The basis of the lexical minimum is the language material. One of the most important and difficult problems, on the solution of which the success of students' education largely depends, is the selection of language material.

The selection of language material is the choice of lexical units, grammatical forms and structures, rules of their use, phonetic and country-specific material in accordance with the stage and profile of training. The problem of language material selection is reflected in the works of such scientists as: Minyar-Beloruhev R.K., Piotrovsky R.G., Rahman S.E., Vishnyakova N.G., Demyanova O.P., Varabanova G.V., Vader E.I., etc. Babinskaya P.K. identifies several approaches to the selection of language material, namely: empirical, pragmatic, methodological and linguistic. [2]. Let's consider the first of the approaches - the empirical approach is the personal experience of a teacher, a methodologist or the author of a textbook, which allows you to correctly determine the lexical minimum only at the initial stage of training. The requirements of communication in a foreign language are revealed in a pragmatic approach. The methodological approach focuses on learning goals, and the linguistic approach includes semantic, grammatical and stylistic criteria.

Thus, Babinskaya P.K. believes that the criteria for the selection of the lexical minimum are the rules for the selection of language material. The linguistic approach includes several criteria for the selection of language material.

The criterion of word compatibility – the expansion of the lexical basis occurs by the ability of the word to combine with other words. The criterion of ambiguity – identifies units that denote several objects or phenomena of reality. The criterion of se-

mantic value is the selection of the most important concepts. The criterion of stylistic neutrality is the exclusion of the use of dialectisms, slang, archaisms, etc. The criterion of word-formation value is aimed at including words that give a large number of derived lexical units. The criterion of formation ability implies the inclusion of prepositions, articles, conjunctions, auxiliary and modal verbs. [2].

Minyar-Beloruhev R.K. wrote that the criteria for selecting language material in a pragmatic approach are:

- the frequency criterion is the frequency of use of a lexical unit in communication, but only the first few hundred words can be distinguished this way, because then the frequency becomes the same;
- the thematic criterion is the definition of topics for the selection of language material, the choice of topic depends on the learning objectives, thus, the thematic criterion complements the criterion of frequency;
- the criterion of useability is semantic and word-formation value, stylistic neutrality, compatibility, formation ability, ambiguity;
- the criterion for describing concepts is the selection of words, assuming a description of the meaning of the word (synonyms);
- the criterion for excluding synonyms is the choice of the most stylistically neutral word from a number of synonyms; the criterion of transparency is the exclusion of phenomena that are understandable by context. [12].

It's suggested to consider the frequency criterion, which is the frequency of the use of lexical units in communication. The thematic criterion refers to the selection of words of a certain subject. The criterion of functionality of lexical units is understood as a set of: compatibility, semantic value, stylistic neutrality, formation ability, word-formation value and ambiguity.

Gasparov B.M. highlights the following provisions for consideration in the selection of language units: a clear allocation and determination of the number of lexical units necessary for assimilation in the learning process; systematization of the lexical minimum that will meet discipline and educational standards; low level of school preparation, not high motivation and monotony of the educational process; increased motivation for language learning in higher education can to promote personality-oriented tasks

and materials that are related to the main field of activity of students. [6].

For example, N.D. Galskova and N.I. Gez distinguish 3 groups for the selection of the lexical minimum, namely: linguistic, statistical and methodological. The linguistic group includes: the principle of semantic value; the principle of compatibility; the principle of word-formation value; the principle of stylistic limitlessness; the principle of polysemy of words; the principle of formation ability; the principle of frequency. The statistical group includes the use of the word, which includes frequency and prevalence as two equivalent components of one indicator. The methodological group is focused on the type of educational institution, goals, standards, content and training programs. [3].

It is important that in addition to the commonly used vocabulary when fulfilling the requirements of the FSES (Federal State Education Standards) program, it is necessary to define a terminological minimum that provides understanding when viewing authentic video material. According to Anisimova A.G., the core of the terminological system should be created by lexical units based on the independent semantics of unknown terms from already known bases. [1].

Anisimova A.G. argues that when viewing authentic materials, students have difficulties with the abundance of new vocabulary and with structural difficulties. Therefore, when selecting a lexical minimum, it is also necessary to determine the syntactic and grammatical minimum, where the most general principles of selection are: functionality, communication, consistency.

To motivate students, the teacher can develop textbooks, manuals, exercises aimed at studying certain terminology. In the collection of exercises, fundamental sections and important concepts can be highlighted. Thus, the tasks of the teacher will include identifying and familiarizing students with these concepts and terms.

Consequently, according to Minyar-Beloruhev R.K., the formation of systemic knowledge through the establishment of interdisciplinary connections is a key concept in the field of higher education. The main criteria in the process of selecting lexical units are: the frequency criterion and the thematic criterion. [12]. Auxiliary criteria are the criterion of the functionality of lexical units. Thus, when selecting a lexical

minimum for university students, it is necessary to first determine the main criteria for selecting lexical material.

Thus, as a result of the selection of language material, basic vocabulary is compiled for different stages and profiles of learning. It is known that the main purpose of teaching a foreign language in higher education is the development of skills and abilities that are necessary for the professional activities of future specialists. Therefore, when teaching students in the fields of "Tourism", "Hotel business", "Management", "Jurisprudence", it is necessary to highlight the needs of this category of specialists. To do this, you need to establish typical situations necessary for using a foreign language.

Gasparov B.M. believes that when selecting lexical material, it is necessary to take into account the structure of the construction of this field of activity, the classification of its sections and their relationship.

It should be noted that when selecting lexical material of any direction, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of the audience and rely on the analysis of lists of criteria. Lexical units for the compilation of the lexical minimum of students of the field of training "Tourism", "Hotel business", "Management", "Jurisprudence" include:

- 1) frequency criterion,
- 2) thematic criterion,
- 3) the criterion of the functionality of lexical units.

Thus, the increase in the lexical minimum is an individual phenomenon, but it is important to take into account the definition of the main criteria for the selection of lexical material for students of non-linguistic universities.

An important fact of using video materials in the classroom is the individualization of learning and motivation to learn. Video recordings include special vocabulary (in our case, terminology for a non-linguistic universities), which contributes to the study of pronunciation, memorization of lexical units in certain communication situations. Thus, video materials create favorable conditions for the formation of both communicative and socio-cultural competence.

The success of students' listening depends on their need and desire to learn something new, the presence of interest in the subject or the topic; all these are subjective factors that form the attitude to cognitive and educational activities. The question arises: what will help direct students' attention to the

perception of new material? These include: the organization of the educational process, the logic of presentation, reliance on previous language experience and reliance on visual clarity.

The success of perception and understanding of foreign speech by ear is influenced by some factors, for example, the pace of speech messages, which includes the speed and accuracy of perception, as well as the effectiveness of memorizing information. It should be noted that the rate of speech consists of two values, namely the number of syllables per minute and speech pauses.

For example, Fedorova M.A. believes that the pace of speech messages also depends on the importance and novelty of information, since important information is reported slower and secondary information is faster. The pace of speech directly depends on the complexity of the topic and the language norm. The study of the tempo of speech is a complex process, because it is associated with rhythm, stress and pauses. Pauses of breathing are a permanent category in a certain language society. In addition to breathing pauses, it is customary to distinguish syntactic and non-syntactic pauses. A distinctive feature of oral speech is hesitation pauses (non-syntactic). These pauses are associated with the speaker's emotion to the communicated information, with self-correction, with the restructuring of syntactic groups, etc. [15].

The success of watching authentic videos and listening lies in the guidelines used by students, in the tips and supports provided to them. These landmarks, supports and hints vary depending on the speech experience and the communication situation. Contact speech (watching an authentic video) takes place in a certain communication situation, increasing the breadth of associative connections. Because this communication provides students with a huge number of landmarks and supports, namely: facial expressions, gestures, intonation, colloquial formulas, repetitions, synonymous expression of the same speech.

Authentic video materials provide a sample of speech and language, special and commonly used vocabulary. Pichugova I.L. believes that the atmosphere of joint viewing, i.e. joint cognitive activity, has an impact on the amount of memorization of information in long-term memory. When a student realizes that he understands a foreign language, his motivation to learn the language increases. [14]. Thus, watching videos expands the scope of education and

increases the practical significance. When watching authentic videos, students' intellectual and creative abilities also develop.

The structural features of the text are divided into external and internal, which include the introductory part, the main communicative part and the final part. [10]. The definition of the difficulty of the text is consistent with the transmission of the main idea, with the form of presentation, namely auditory and audiovisual. Leontiev A.A. distinguishes texts into three groups, which differ in certain degrees of complexity, for example: simple texts are semi-authentic texts, popular science and art style, which include a simple narrative; texts of medium difficulty are a genre of conversation in which authentic or semi-authentic texts are transmitted; difficult texts are authentic texts (interview, reportage, conversation, description). [10, p. 95-100].

As already mentioned, factors and conditions determine the peculiarities of oral communication at all levels of the language, as well as the complexity of perceiving information by ear. In this paper, we are interested in the lexical difficulties encountered by students when viewing authentic video material. To increase the vocabulary and its diversity, the figurative meaning of words and their use, string words (without informative load), phraseological turns, amorphous (unmotivated) words are added. When watching a video with such material, it is necessary to keep in mind the situation and context, because the word that was learned earlier will be heard instead of the desired word in a certain context.

According to I.L. Pechurova, the objectives of listening training include: perception of the interlocutor's foreign speech in different communication situations; understanding authentic texts with varying degrees of complexity and understanding their content. [7]. Students of language universities are faced with more complex tasks, in particular: to master the full ability of listening with an understanding of the text of a television and radio program, the perception of films of a cognitive, regional, journalistic nature, reports, interviews, etc.

The system of exercises aimed at teaching listening has the following tasks: the ratio of exercises to the psychological and linguistic nature of messages; the relationship of listening with other types of speech, for example, with speaking; the successful

implementation of the practical goal. In the Russian methodology, the following subsystems of exercises are distinguished: training and speech, or preparatory and communicative. Training exercises are aimed at the technical side, at removing psychological and linguistic difficulties of text perception, at developing the ability to understand both text and microtext. Speech exercises are aimed at developing the perception of speech messages in authentic conditions, without supports and prompts.

Pavlova E.A. notes that the use of video recordings in the classroom is justified, because teachers are able to hold the attention of students and influence the audience. Information that is provided in a visual form is more accessible to perception and is absorbed faster and easier. When viewing, speakers, facial expressions, gestures are visible, emotions are felt, information about the place, appearance, non-verbal behavior of carriers in certain communication situations is transmitted. In this way, students can see and feel the text more deeply, as well as interpret it. [8]. As a result, one of the educational tasks is being implemented and it is vocabulary expansion.

Summing up all of the said above, we can conclude that the use of authentic video in foreign language classes is an integral part of the training in higher education of students in the areas of training "Management", "Tourism", "Hotel business". Students will have a broader outlook. Memorizing unfamiliar vocabulary and mastering special terminology will be more productive.

Consequently, the ability to correctly perceive what has been listened to leads to an understanding of the internal logical relationships of the text. [5]. A student who speaks a foreign language at the level of a native speaker is able to compare the content, language form and communication situation, namely, he can separate objective information from subjective.

Thus, as a result of the analysis of the feasibility of using authentic video materials in foreign language classes, we can conclude that the effectiveness consists in individualization of learning and motivation to learn. Authentic audio and video materials are a sample of speech and language, special and general cultural vocabulary, which contribute to a more accelerated and effective assimilation of the material by students in foreign language classes.

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